

GLACIER STRUCTURE OF THE EASTERN PART OF WINTER ISLAND ACCORDING TO GEORADAR DATA

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During the wintering period, monitoring GPR studies of glaciers on the islands adjacent to the Ukrainian Antarctic Akademik Vernadsky station are carried out. The purpose of the studies is to track the seasonal dynamics of the appearance of new near-surface cracks and to detect structural changes in the glacier body that are associated with the internal movement of the ice mass. These works use data obtained by a Transient Technologies VIY3-300 ground penetrating radar.

After interpreting the ground penetrating radar data obtained on the eastern part of the Winter Island glacier, it was found that under the influence of gravity, a main fault was formed in the body of the glacier, or rather, a zone of contraction, which divides the glacier into upper and lower. This boundary is clearly visible in the field of reflected electromagnetic waves and has the appearance of an elongated, almost horizontal in-phase wave field, which is traced along the entire length of the glacier. The thickness of this boundary does not exceed one meter.

The lower part of the glacier lies on rocks with a complex relief, which has protrusions of more than one meter. They significantly limit the mobility of the lower part of the glacier. The identified fault structures (shear zones in the plastic substance) in the lower part of the glacier are formed by protrusions of rocks.

The upper part of the glacier has a clear structure created by four blocks separated by shear faults. The surface of these blocks has a different slope, but they move in the same direction but at different speeds. In the middle of the ice blocks, there are firn horizons with different reflection coefficients of electromagnetic waves. They help to recreate the block structure of the glacier.

The best materials were obtained in early spring to reproduce the block structure of glaciers and study the rate of snow accumulation. These data do not have diffraction hodographs, which complicate wave fields and introduce artifacts into the final fault-block model of the glacier.

However, it is necessary to use data obtained in the summer to identify the locations of fault initiation and study the qualitative and quantitative indicators of changes occurring in glacial fault structures. At this time of year, meltwater fills the inter-fault space, allowing for the detection of barely noticeable faults.